

Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation of Herbal Kajal

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ABSTRACT

Historically known as kohl or surma, kajal is applied as an eye-catching cosmetic. An ancient eye Cosmetic is kajal. In addition to being used as a cosmetic, There are a number of endemic ocular diseases In the Nile region including trachoma – which is caused by a chlamydial bacterium and can cause corneal Scarring – and conjunctival cicatricial disease, with visual loss, kohl was also used medicinally to darken The eyelids and protect the eyes from infectious diseases. Most women use it, while some men and kids Also use it. Depending on the culture and country, kohl has different ingredients and preparation methods. The use of homemade, lead-based eyeliner has increased. The idea behind the manufacture of herbal kajal using medicinal plants for improvement is both a fresh And a revolutionary technique. Ghee, coconut oil, and camphor are all natural substances we used to Create our kajal formulations. The main advantages of these cosmetics products improved patient Compliance, water resistance, durability, and side effect freedom costeffective shaping Curve. Herbal Kajal contains castor oil helps in providing coolness to the eyes, and gives the eyes relief from Stress, Coconut oil has antibacterial, anti-parasitic, antiviral & anti-inflammatory properties almond oil Content vitamin k and vitamin A revealed that the values fell within the permitted ranges by Based on Various physiochemical criteria, standardisation of the herbs was carried out. Its antimicrobial activity And a few other factors were used to compare it to similar items. Based on chosen parameters and its Anti-microbial capacity, the herbal kajal has been compared to reference items.

INTRODUCTION

Eyes are the important connections between the outer and inner worlds. For the element Of fire and light that governs our eyes pitta dosha stands for that in Ayurveda. Hence eyes are very Important organ in our body system. For care and beautification of eyes Vedic science offers several

Natural, safe and effective techniques. With the help of science of ayurveda, several herbs and floras Were used to make Ayurvedic cosmetics that not only beautified the skin but as well as act as the Shield against any kind of external affects for the body. In cosmetics for useful purposes such

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as Moisturizing, whitening, colouring, sunscreen, antioxidant, immunostimulant, cleansing, Preservatives, thickeners, etc. plants products are also used. Role of kajal in eye products can't be Ignored as it is one of those products. Kajal is worn for many reasons including tradition, beautification, to ward off the "evil eye". It is the widespread belief that kohl is medically beneficial for the eyes, and finally because wearing kohl is encouraged within the sunna, the traditional behavioural guidelines of the Islamic religion [1]. There are number of plants which are used ophthalmic disorders, either single or in compound formulations are present in the Ayurvedic system of medicine, as mentioned in ancient Indian books like Charak Samhita, Sushrut Samhita, Bhav prakasha, Ras Tarang, Nayan Drastam and Astanghriday. Various eye disorders and diseases like Abhishyand (Conjunctivitis), Adhimanth (Glaucoma), Timir (Cataract), etc. have been described in great details in Ayurveda. (Indian system of medicine). Their etiology and treatments have also been described. Use of Various herbal drugs in different dosage forms like extract, arka (aqueous distillate), kajal (collerium), and fomentation and washing with different extracts have also been prescribed frequently [2]. Not only the use of animals for laboratory testing but also with the use of materials and ingredients derived from animal sources is the concern in this area. For the standards and quality of drugs and cosmetics manufactured and sold in India the Drugs and Cosmetic act is concerned.

OBJECTIVES:

Inorganic kajal, which is made up of dangerous chemicals. Over time, these compounds can seriously damage a person's natural beauty and possibly put them at danger for health problems. In order to treat eye inflammation and reduce eye redness, medicated herbal kajal is prepared. Herbal kajal works by relaxing and strengthening the eye

muscles, which enhances the eye's general functionality.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials

Sr. no	Ingredient name	Quantity
1.	Almond oil	50ml
2.	Coconut Oil	100ml
3.	Dill Seeds	6gm
4.	Cow Ghee	2gm
5.	Castor Oil	2ml
6.	Cotton	2gm

Tab I – Composition of Herbal Kajal

METHODOLOGY

Make a wick by wrapping the seeds of dill in a muslin cloth.

The muslin cloth piece used as a wick & was lighted in a mud lamp containing almond oil and coconut oil.

The black soot was collected in a clean, dry porcelain.

The powder then mixed with cow ghee to form a paste form. i.e. kajal.

Preliminary Ayurveda Formulation of Kajal

1. Lit the lamp and put the inverted copper plate

2. Black soot is obtained on copper

3.Srape the black soot and collect it.

4.Formulated herbal kajal

Method of Preparation of Herbal Kajal

RESULT & DISSCUSSION

Evaluation Test of Herbal Kajal

Physical Test

Sr. No	Parameter	Evaluation
1	Colour	Dark Black
2	Odour	Characteristic Odour
3	Texture	Smooth
4	Consistency	Semi Solid

Tab II – Physical Properties

pH Test - The pH was determined by using the pH strip was 6.5

Skin Irritation test - No irritation observed after application on skin.

Stability test –

Sr no	Parameter	At room temperature	At 40°C temperature
1	Colour	No change	No change
2	Odour	No change	No change
3	Consistency	No change	No change

Tab III -Stability Test

Microbial test -

There was no signs of microbial growth after 24 hours of incubation at 37°C and it was comparable with the control.

Fig IX – Microbial Test Observations

Spreadability test –

The cream sample was applied between the two glass slides and was compressed between the two-glass slide to uniform thickness by placing 100 gm of weight for 5 minutes then weight was added to the weighing pan. The time in which the upper glass slide moved over the lower slide was taken as a measure of spread ability.

Spreadability = 8.5

DISCUSSION

Since ancient civilizations, mostly Hindu and Muslim religious regions like India, Rome, Afghanistan, Egypt, China, and Japan, kajal has been used for eye decoration as well as defence against and treatment of various eye diseases like bacterial conjunctivitis and bacterial keratitis. Eye cosmetics are as old as vanity, according to reports from Unani, Ayurveda, Greko-Arabica systems of medicine literature, etc. Kajal use as cosmetics and Mediherbal kajal is prepared and evaluated by Different parameter. Evaluation test Result shows pH, Anti-microbial, Spreadability result.

CONCLUSION

In India more than 70 % of the populations use herbal cosmetics for their health care. Herbal kohl is formulated, and scientific intent is used for selection of ingredients. The chemical formulation of herbal kajal products includes addition of various natural additives like waxes, oils natural color, natural fragrances and parts of plants like leaves, etc. The advantages of herbal kohl are lower cost, side effects free, environmental friendly, safe to use etc. Also, it has a great future ahead as compared to the synthetic cosmetics.

Proper regulation of these herbs and standardization will lead to tremendous and significant growth in herbal cosmetics field.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors have no conflicts of interest regarding this investigation.

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